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Abstract book

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Brachytherapy re-irradiation in gynecological cancers

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During the last few decades, there has been a significant progress in the field of radiotherapy of gynecological malignancies. A progress in external beam radiotherapy, with the modern intensity-modulated radiotherapy, Volumetric modulated Arc therapy, Stereotactic body radiotherapy techniques, and also the clinical implementation of 3D brachytherapy based on CT or, even better, MR planning, led to increased survival and loco-regional control rates in this group of patients.

However, despite these improvements in therapy and prognosis, a certain number of patients will still develop a disease relapse, sometimes inside the volume of tissue previously treated with radiotherapy. Re-irradiation in this group of patients is one of the possible treatment options, but it is not an easy task, and it is associated with lower survival rates and an increased risk of developing G3/4 post-irradiation toxicity than during the first line of radiotherapy.

In the terms of re-irradiation, in patients with local gynecological tumor relapse, when the relapsed tumor is accessible with brachytherapy applicator systems, brachytherapy is an ideal radiotherapy technique. Brachytherapy is characterized by high doses of radiation that are delivered to the tissue in the immediate vicinity of the radioactive source, and the steep dose cut-off ensures the minimization of the effect to the surrounding organs at risk.

Several papers have been published that addressed the topic of implementation of brachytherapy in re-irradiation, with very interesting results and conclusions that could be used as a basis for treatment approach, since precise protocols still do not exist.

Keywords: tumor relapse, reirradiation, brachytherapy

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